

A STUDY ON DETERMINANTS OF SATISFACTION LEVEL FOR MSME BORROWERS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a crucial role in an economy. They generate huge employment opportunities, help in equitable distribution of income and wealth and reduce regional disparities in economic development of the country. The MSME entrepreneurs can prosper only if they get required support from the banks for credit facilities and other banking services. This study is conducted with the purpose of exploring factors influencing satisfaction of MSME borrowers and studying the satisfaction level of MSME borrowers with the banks. Suggestions are made to improve their satisfaction level so that the MSME sector may grow at a fast pace. MSMEs' satisfaction with commercial banks is examined in this study using scientific methods. It has been discovered that all connections between variables and customer satisfaction with commercial bank policy and procedures are linear, and the correlation coefficients are very high, suggesting that a connection exists between the two.

2680

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Introduction

The MSMEs generate huge employment opportunities and require lesser amount of capital vis-à-vis large industrial units. They help in equitable distribution of income and wealth among people of the country whereas large industries result in concentration of wealth with a few individuals. MSMEs reduce regional disparities in economic development of the country through industrialization of rural and backward areas.

The place MSME sector occupies in the Indian economy can be ascertained from the fact that there are 633.88 lakh MSMEs in which 11.10 crore people are employed (*Ministry of MSME Annual Report 2020-21*). The sector contributes 30 per cent to the nation's GDP and accounts for 49 per cent of Indian exports (*Business Today* February 7, 2021).

However, our MSME entrepreneurs still face a number of challenges like arranging adequate finance, marketing the products, updating the

technology, equipping themselves with entrepreneurial skills, obtaining various types of Government approvals and competing with the large industries. Arranging adequate and timely finance is a major problem for an entrepreneur. As per an estimate, the overall credit gap in the MSME sector is Rs. 20 to 25 trillion (*Reserve Bank of India* 2019).

Scheduled commercial banks provide 81 per cent of the total credit provided by the formal financial sector to the MSMEs in India (*International Finance Corporation* 2018). Therefore, providing adequate finance and other financial services to MSMEs by banks is a prerequisite for growth of our MSME sector. In view of above, it's critical to know whether banking companies are able to offer sufficient financial services to their MSME borrowers when looking at customer satisfaction in banking. Currently, researchers are looking at how satisfied the MSME borrowers are with the financial services they have access to, as well as their potential future behaviour. Current research helps us gather data on MSME customers' perceptions and satisfaction with available banking services so as to close the knowledge gap between customers' expectations and customers' perceptions of the services delivered and consumed.

Objectives of the Study

This study has been carried out with the following objectives:

1. To explore factors affecting satisfaction level of MSME borrowers;
2. To study the satisfaction level of MSME borrowers with the banks;
3. To offer suggestions to improve satisfaction level of MSME borrowers.

Literature Review

MSMEs form the backbone of our Economy. They account for a large portion of our industrial output and employment. Financing to this sector is of critical importance, particularly as it benefits the weakest sections (of the society). (Arun Jaitley, the Indian Finance Minister July 10, 2014). (Kannan and Sudalaimuthu 2014).

MSMEs have played an important role in improving the lifestyle of people and in social development. These have also helped in economic development by providing employment to people but they face problems related to finance, employees, technology, innovation etc. (Appasaba et al. 2013).

MSMEs primarily suffer from the problems of lack of bank credit, competition from multinational companies, poor infrastructure, unavailability of raw material and other inputs, lack of advanced technology, lack of marketing channels, lack of training and skill development and complex labour laws and red tape. MSME owners are not innovative and their entrepreneurial skills are low (Ali and Husain 2014). They are also facing the problems of financial constraints, power shortage and raw material procurement (Aruna 2015).

The MSMEs face a number of challenges while seeking credit facilities from the banks and during their day-to-day transactions with the banks. The application and supporting documents required by the bank are huge and it is a time-consuming job. The MSMEs do not receive adequate Bank support for expansion of business. Loan repayment schedule fixed by the bank is inappropriate. The bank rules and regulations need to be made easier for MSMEs. The borrowers in general are not happy with the behavior of bank personnel. Banks should not only provide loan but should also assist MSMEs by providing more logistic, operational, marketing and export services. Financial pattern of the banks should be changed and they should also work as facilitators (Ali 2015).

Bank financing is the most popular source for financing SMEs in India. The SME financing schemes provide credit to this sector at low rates of interest and at attractive conditions but the procedure involved is lengthy. Moreover, too much of documentation is required. Insufficient collateral and biasness are also the major problems (Saravanan 2013).

Satisfaction is a very important element in relationship of bank and MSME. Flexible response of the bank to changing business

needs is a factor having major impact on satisfaction of MSME with the policy of commercial banks concerning MSMEs. Granting of loans considering business needs, offering appropriate financial services to business, creating favourable loan conditions are the other factors having major impact on MSME satisfaction (Jureviciene and Skvarciany 2013).

Theoretical Model

Different researchers have used different models to assess the MSME borrowers' and general customers' satisfaction level with the banks and the quality of their customer service. Siddiq (2013) used SERVQUAL method to study the MSME entrepreneurs' perception of service quality of nationalised banks in Coimbatore district. Praveenkumar (2016), Sawant (2016) and Koirala (2012) applied this model to study the quality of customer service and level of customer satisfaction in banks. The SERVQUAL method, developed by Parasuraman et al. (1985), has five dimensions, viz., Reliability, Assurance, Tangibles, Empathy and Responsiveness.

Shanka (2012) has used SERVPERF model to measure the quality of service offered by the banks. Fragoso and Espinoza (2017) evaluated the quality of services provided by the banks in Mexico through a modified version of SERVPERF by designing an instrument consisting of 12 of the total 22 items under the model. The SERVPERF model was developed out of the SERVQUAL model by Cronin and Taylor (1992). SERVPERF model also has five dimensions as mentioned above, viz., Reliability, Assurance, Tangibles, Empathy and Responsiveness. The difference between SERVQUAL and SERVPERF models is that while under former model, the quality of service can be measured by identifying the gaps between consumers' expectations of the service and their perceptions of the actual service, the latter measures service quality by using perceptions of the customers.

Maswadeh (2015) applied CARTER model to evaluate the degree of satisfaction of MSMEs on the service quality provided by the Jordanian Islamic banks. The CARTER model has six dimensions, viz., Compliance,

Assurance, Reliability, Tangibility, Empathy and Responsiveness. CARTER model was developed by Othman and Owen (2001). This model has an additional dimension of Compliance, besides the five dimensions of SERVQUAL and SERVPERF models. Compliance refers to complying with the Islamic principles in operation of banking services.

Avkiran (1994) developed BANKSERV model, which contains four dimensions of service quality, viz., Staff conduct, Credibility, Communication and Access to ATM services. Olaniyan et al. (2020) applied BANKSERV model in his study to measure the quality of service and client satisfaction in Peruvian financial sector. Pandey (2018) adopted BANKSERV model with some modifications for assessing customer perceptions of service quality in banking industry. This model excludes many important dimensions, particularly in reference to the 'borrower' segment of the bank customers.

Bahia and Nantel (2000) developed the Banking Service Quality (BSQ) model which contains six dimensions, viz., Effectiveness and Assurance, Access, Price, Tangibles, Services portfolio and Reliability. Abdullah et al. (2011) applied BSQ model to have an insight regarding factors affecting service quality within the banking sector. Hamzagic and Tournois (2021) applied Bank Service Quality (BSQ) scale, after adding a couple of items therein, to capture customers' evaluation of the service quality of banks.

BANKQUAL model, proposed by Tsoukatos and Mastrojianni (2010) has four dimensions, viz., Assurance and empathy, Effectiveness, Reliability and Confidence. Poornima et al. (2019) applied BANKQUAL model to analyse the service quality of banks. Ariffin et al. (2014) applied the BANKQUAL model to compare the service quality of local banks and foreign banks. Some researchers have made a comparison of different models for assessing banks' customer satisfaction.

Vanparia and Soukatos (2013) studied the SERVQUAL, SERVPERF, BSQ and BANKQUAL scales in banking sector and found that different models of service quality have different psychometric properties of measurement model. The measures

developed internationally are of little use in determining service quality of Indian banks.

Sangeetha and Mahalingham (2011) have found that service quality has some common dimensions across the different models but the items involved and their operationalisation in different cultural contexts within the same banking sector may vary.

Some researchers have developed their own model for assessing customer satisfaction. Kanchana and Sankaranarayanan (2020) have considered the dimensions Loan procedures, Interest rate, Bank officials' attitude, Loan sanctioning time, Bank guidance and Bank's guarantee services while assessing the level of satisfaction in sanctioning of loan by the banks.

While evaluating the perception of micro enterprises towards the services rendered by public sector banks in Tirunelveli district, Vijaya (2018) has considered for components, viz., Friendly attitude towards customers, E-services, Bank overdraft facility and interest and the Loan repayment. Each of the four components were divided into 7 to 15 variables.

Among above models, SERVQUAL is the most popular model as it has most of the important dimensions of the service quality for assessing the customer satisfaction level. However, this model does not include certain variables like Transparency, On-line banking service, Bank's trustworthiness and Security of the borrower's personal information with the bank, which are crucial to the MSME borrowers. In the present paper, all these variables have been included, besides the variables contained in SERVQUAL model.

Factors Influencing Satisfaction of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises with the Policy and Procedures of Commercial Banks

The policy of commercial banks concerning MSMEs can be described as bank activities directed to support business of micro, small and medium enterprises. For this reason, MSMEs select and remain with a bank that can meet their needs. There are many scientists analysing satisfaction of micro, small and medium enterprises with bank activities

focused on MSME commerce support and determinants having impact on it. The survival of banks depends on customer satisfaction (Kaura 2013). One study found the price competitiveness, credit availability, perceived service quality, staff attributes and bank attributes as determinants of perceived bank selection (Narteh 2013). Another study considered the following factors to ascertain perception of MSME borrowers towards services rendered by banks: service of the staff, rate of interest, repayment period, sanctioning time, procedural formalities, instalments, loan granting system, issue of notice, collateral requirement and processing fee (Siddiq and Sathyaprasad 2017). In another study the researcher has investigated the impact of quality of banking services, variety of banking services, accessibility of banking services and price of banking services on small and medium sized companies' satisfaction with banks' business oriented services (Skvarciany 2014). In a study on SME customers satisfaction with the Jordanian Islamic banks, the researcher considered the dimensions of empathy, reliability, responsiveness, tangibles, assurance and compliance (Maswadeh 2015).

MSMEs evaluate their banking relationship based on the effectiveness and quality of banks' service outcomes and on the care and manner in which bankers deliver services (Lundahl et al. 2009). Progress of the relationship between the bank and its corporate clients depends on various factors: industry trust, mutual interest dependence, the state of conflict and co-operation and overall closeness or distance of the relationship as well as on the partners' mutual expectations (Zineldin 1996). Fairness is an element that is positively related to customer satisfaction (Zhu and Chen 2012). In another study, the researcher has used the factors like quantity of documentation, simplicity of rules, arrangement for start-up cost, reasons for default, conflict of partners, bank support for business expansion, bribe for bank loan, behaviour of bank personnel and loan repayment schedule for ascertaining the MSMEs' perception about banks' financing in Bangladesh (Ali 2015).

In a study for the analysis of bank's policy towards business, seven factors determining this policy were identified: provision of credit according to needs; provision of necessary financial services; creating favourable conditions for business loans; flexible reactions towards changing needs of business; provision of support for businesses experiencing successful periods; provision of support in critical moments of a business enterprise; timely financial decision making (Mačerinskienė et al. 2012).

Although there are many different factors influencing satisfaction of micro, small and medium enterprises with the policy of commercial banks concerning MSMEs, the following elements have been selected for the present research:

1. Timely decisions: This refers to a smooth loan granting system and providing prompt

solution to customers' problems through simple and transparent procedures of the bank;

2. Loan adequacy: This refers to granting adequate loan as per customer's requirement, acting in a trustworthy manner;

3. Appropriate financial services: This includes a high quality on-line and counter service, easy accessibility of bank's higher management and a smooth monitoring and recovery procedure;

4. Favourable loan conditions: This refers to the provision of favourable loan conditions by the bank, viz., sympathetic, competent and trained staff with empathy for customers and always willing to help, capable of keeping the customers' personal information fully secured.

Based on the above study the following Research Model is suggested.

Figure 1. Research Model

Source: Designed by the authors

Methodology of the Study

There are two types of bank's customers, i.e., depositor and borrower. In the current study, the researchers considered the latter, i.e., MSME borrowers of NCR Delhi availing loan in different ways from the commercial banks. In order to obtain the perception of

MSME borrowers on above four elements, the primary data were collected through a structured Questionnaire containing 16 closed-ended questions on the five-point Likert Scale. The details of questions formulated to gather MSME borrowers'

perception on above four elements are as under:

Table 1. Elements of MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction and the Relevant Questions

Element	Questions Formulated
Timely decisions	Prompt solution to problems Simple procedural formalities Loan granting system Transparency in procedures
Loan adequacy	Sufficient amount of loan Banks’ trustworthiness in important matters
Appropriate financial services	On-line banking service Counter service in branches Bank management accessibility Monitoring and recovery procedure
Favourable loan conditions	Sympathetic and reassuring attitude Employees trained in customer handling Employees willing to help Security of customers’ personal information Bank employees’ empathy Staff competence to resolve queries

Source: Designed by the authors

Selection of Sample Respondents

The research is conducted among MSME borrowers of commercial banks for analysing and measuring their satisfaction with the services rendered by banks. The total respondents were 104 borrowers in the NCR Delhi.

Measurement Techniques

Indeed, satisfaction measurement is a difficult job, and it is also difficult to conduct any psychological study. In the proposed study bank’s customer satisfaction is measured by the specific techniques. The present study was conducted by Summated scale that is Likert scale. Such type of scale consists of some statements, which express either a favourable or unfavourable attitude toward the given object to which the respondent is asked to react.

Processing and Analysis of Data

Collected data were processed and analysed by way of using quantitative techniques.

Basically, descriptive and empirical analyses were conducted. For ascertaining the characteristics of data, descriptive analysis and interpretations were drawn by percentage frequency, mean and standard deviation (SD). Also, empirical analyses were depicted by the Pearson's coefficient. The Excel programme was used for calculation of Chronbach’s Alpha and the Correlation coefficient (Pearson r). The statistical computer package SPSS version 26.0 was also used for authentic analysis for all the cases.

Reliability of the Questionnaire

Cronbach’s alpha test was conducted to see if multiple-question Likert scale surveys are reliable. These questions measure latent variables - hidden or unobservable variables like: a person’s conscientiousness, neurosis or openness.

Observed value of Cronbach’s Alpha, calculated through Excel programme, is 0.994, which is much above the accepted value of 0.7. So, the questionnaire is reliable.

Table 2. MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Banks provide prompt and timely solutions to all problems’

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent

Valid	Strongly disagree	23	22.1	22.1	22.1
	Disagree	30	28.8	28.8	51.0
	Neither agree nor disagree	10	9.6	9.6	60.6
	Agree	20	19.2	19.2	79.8
	Strongly agree	21	20.2	20.2	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 2.MSME Borrowers' Satisfaction on 'Banks provide prompt and timely solutions to all problems'

2686

Source: Designed by the authors

About 'Banks provide prompt and timely solutions to all problems' it was observed that 23(22.1%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 30(28.8%) respondents responded Disagree, 10(9.6%) respondents responded

Neither agree nor disagree, 20(19.2%) respondents responded Agree and 21(20.2%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	14	13.5	13.5	13.5
	Disagree	33	31.7	31.7	45.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	22	21.2	21.2	66.3
	Agree	14	13.5	13.5	79.8
	Strongly agree	21	20.2	20.2	100.0

	Total	104	100.0	100.0	
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Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 3.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Banks have simple procedural formalities making the loan process easy’

Source: Designed by the authors

2687

About ‘Banks have simple procedural formalities making the loan process easy’ it was observed that 14(13.5%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 33(31.7%) respondents responded Disagree, 22(21.2%)

respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 14(13.5%) respondents responded Agree and 21(20.2%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

Table 4.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘As a customer you are satisfied with the Loan granting system of banks’

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	18	17.3	17.3	17.3
	Disagree	36	34.6	34.6	51.9
	Neither agree nor disagree	14	13.5	13.5	65.4
	Agree	20	19.2	19.2	84.6

	Strongly agree	16	15.4	15.4	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 4. MSME Borrowers' Satisfaction on 'As a customer you are satisfied with the Loan granting system of banks'

Source: Designed by the authors

About 'As a customer you are satisfied with the Loan granting system of banks' it was observed that 18(17.3%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 36(34.6%) respondents responded Disagree, 14(13.5%)

respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 20(19.2%) respondents responded Agree and 16(15.4%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

2688

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	26	25.0	25.0	25.0
	Disagree	19	18.3	18.3	43.3
	Neither agree nor disagree	23	22.1	22.1	65.4
	Agree	16	15.4	15.4	80.8
	Strongly agree	20	19.2	19.2	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 5. MSME Borrowers Satisfaction on 'Banks keep transparency in the procedures'

Source: Designed by the authors

About 'Banks keep transparency in the procedures' it was observed that 26(25%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 19(18.3%) respondents responded Disagree,

23(22.1%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 16(15.4%) respondents responded Agree and 20(19.2%) respondents responded Strongly agree

2689

Table 6. MSME Borrowers' Satisfaction on 'Banks' loan monitoring and recovery procedure are borrower-friendly'

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	16	15.4	15.4	15.4
	Disagree	38	36.5	36.5	51.9
	Neither agree nor disagree	16	15.4	15.4	67.3
	Agree	17	16.3	16.3	83.7

	Strongly agree	17	16.3	16.3	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 6. MSME Borrowers' Satisfaction on 'Banks' loan monitoring and recovery procedure are borrower-friendly'

Source: Designed by the authors

About 'Banks' loan monitoring and recovery procedure are borrower-friendly' it was observed that 16(15.4%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 38(36.5%) respondents responded Disagree, 16(15.4%)

respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 17(16.3%) respondents responded Agree and 17(16.3%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	21	20.2	20.2	20.2
	Disagree	25	24.0	24.0	44.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	14	13.5	13.5	57.7
	Agree	22	21.2	21.2	78.8

	Strongly agree	22	21.2	21.2	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 7. MSME Borrowers' Satisfaction on 'On-line banking service is very useful'

Source: Designed by the authors

About 'On-line banking service is very useful' it was observed that 21(20.2%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 25(24%) respondents responded Disagree, 14(13.5%)

respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 22(21.2%) respondents responded Agree and 22(21.2%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

2691

Table 8. MSME Borrowers' Satisfaction on 'Banks are sympathetic and reassuring towards their customers'

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	26	25.0	25.0	25.0
	Disagree	30	28.8	28.8	53.8
	Neither agree nor disagree	12	11.5	11.5	65.4
	Agree	16	15.4	15.4	80.8
	Strongly agree	20	19.2	19.2	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 8.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Banks are sympathetic and reassuring towards their customers’

Source: Designed by the authors

About ‘Banks are sympathetic and reassuring towards their customers’ it was observed that 26(25%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 30(28.8%) respondents responded Disagree, 12(11.5%) respondents responded

Neither agree nor disagree, 16(15.4%) respondents responded Agree and 20(19.2%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

2692

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	13	12.5	12.5	12.5
	Disagree	31	29.8	29.8	42.3
	Neither agree nor disagree	28	26.9	26.9	69.2
	Agree	16	15.4	15.4	84.6
	Strongly agree	16	15.4	15.4	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 9.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Bank employees are trained in customer handling’

Source: Designed by the authors

About ‘Bank employees are trained in customer handling’ it was observed that 13(12.5%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 31(29.8%) respondents responded

Disagree, 28(26.9%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 16(15.4%) respondents responded Agree and 16(15.4%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

Table 10.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Bank employees are willing to help customers’

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	23	22.1	22.1	22.1
	Disagree	26	25.0	25.0	47.1
	Neither agree nor disagree	24	23.1	23.1	70.2
	Agree	28	26.9	26.9	97.1
	Strongly agree	3	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

2693

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 10.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Bank employees are willing to help customers’

Source: Designed by the authors

About 'Bank employees are willing to help customers' it was observed that 23(22.1%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 26(25%) respondents responded Disagree and 24(23.1%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree whereas 28(26.9%) respondents responded Agree and 3(2.9%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	16	15.4	15.4	15.4
	Disagree	28	26.9	26.9	42.3
	Neither agree nor disagree	20	19.2	19.2	61.5
	Agree	20	19.2	19.2	80.8
	Strongly agree	20	19.2	19.2	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 11. MSME Borrowers' Satisfaction on 'Banks are trustworthy in dealing with important matters'

Source: Designed by the authors

About 'Banks are trustworthy in dealing with important matters' it was observed that 16(15.4%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 28(26.9%) respondents responded Disagree, 20(19.2%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 20(19.2%) respondents responded Agree and 20(19.2%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	19	18.3	18.3	18.3
	Disagree	41	39.4	39.4	57.7

	Neither agree nor disagree	20	19.2	19.2	76.9
	Strongly agree	24	23.1	23.1	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 12.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Personal information of customers is secured with the banks’

Source: Designed by the authors

About ‘Personal information of customers is secured with the banks’ it was observed that 19(18.3%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 41(39.4%) respondents responded

Disagree and 20(19.2%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree whereas 24(23.1%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	24	23.1	23.1	23.1
	Disagree	37	35.6	35.6	58.7
	Neither agree nor disagree	14	13.5	13.5	72.1
	Agree	14	13.5	13.5	85.6
	Strongly agree	15	14.4	14.4	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 13.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Bank management is easily accessible to customers for help’

Source: Designed by the authors

About ‘Bank management is easily accessible to customers for help’ it was observed that 24(23.1%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 37(35.6%) respondents responded Disagree, 14(13.5%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 14(13.5%) respondents responded Agree and 15(14.4%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

2696

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	19	18.3	18.3	18.3
	Disagree	32	30.8	30.8	49.0
	Neither agree nor disagree	18	17.3	17.3	66.3
	Agree	21	20.2	20.2	86.5
	Strongly agree	14	13.5	13.5	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 14.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Banks sanction sufficient amount of loan as per requirement’

Source: Designed by the authors

About ‘Banks sanction sufficient amount of loan as per requirement’ it was observed that 19(18.3%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 32(30.8%) respondents responded

Disagree, 18(17.3%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree and 21(20.2%) respondents responded Agree and 14(13.5%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

2697

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	24	23.1	23.1	23.1
	Disagree	31	29.8	29.8	52.9
	Neither agree nor disagree	27	26.0	26.0	78.8
	Agree	19	18.3	18.3	97.1
	Strongly agree	3	2.9	2.9	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 15.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Banks provide good counter service in branches’

Source: Designed by the authors

About ‘Banks provide good counter service in branches’ it was observed that 24(23.1%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 31(29.8%) respondents responded Disagree

and 27(26%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree whereas 19(18.3%) respondents responded Agree and 3(2.9%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

Table 16. MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Banks staff have empathy towards customers in resolving their issues’

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	14	13.5	13.5	13.5
	Disagree	32	30.8	30.8	44.2
	Neither agree nor disagree	22	21.2	21.2	65.4
	Agree	21	20.2	20.2	85.6
	Strongly agree	15	14.4	14.4	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 16.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Banks staff have empathy towards customers in resolving their issues’

Source: Designed by the authors

About ‘Banks staff have empathy towards customers in resolving their issues’ it was observed that 14(13.5%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 32(30.8%) respondents responded Disagree, 22(21.2%)

respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 21(20.2%) respondents responded Agree and 15(14.4%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

Table 17.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Bank staff is competent to resolve all queries of customers’

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly disagree	19	18.3	18.3	18.3
	Disagree	36	34.6	34.6	52.9
	Neither agree nor disagree	16	15.4	15.4	68.3
	Agree	13	12.5	12.5	80.8
	Strongly agree	20	19.2	19.2	100.0
	Total	104	100.0	100.0	

Source: Designed by the authors

Figure 17.MSME Borrowers’ Satisfaction on ‘Bank staff is competent to resolve all queries of customers’

Source: Designed by the authors

About ‘Bank staff is competent to resolve all queries of customers’ it was observed that 19(18.3%) respondents responded Strongly disagree, 36(34.6%) respondents responded Disagree, 16(15.4%) respondents responded Neither agree nor disagree, 13(12.5%) respondents responded Agree and 20(19.2%) respondents responded Strongly agree.

Pearson’s Correlation coefficient, Mean and Standard Deviation

The correlation analysis was made to measure the relationship between the factors investigated. The correlation (Pearson r) values, along with mean and standard deviation, are given in the following table:

Table 18.Corporate Policy and Procedure wise Mean, Standard Deviation and Correlation

Sl. No.	Corporate policies and procedures	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation (Pearson r) Observed Values
1	Banks provide prompt and timely solutions to all problems	2.87	1.475	0.906
2	Banks have simple procedural formalities making the loan process easy	2.95	1.347	0.918
3	As a customer you are satisfied with the loan granting system of banks	2.81	1.352	0.912
4	Banks keep transparency in the procedures	2.86	1.451	0.894
5	Banks’ loan monitoring and recovery procedure are borrower-friendly	2.82	1.335	0.922
6	On-line banking service is very useful	2.99	1.458	0.939
7	Banks are sympathetic and reassuring towards their customers	2.75	1.473	0.902
8	Bank employees are trained in customer handling	2.91	1.255	0.855
9	Bank employees are willing to help customers	2.63	1.183	0.884
10	Banks are trustworthy in dealing with important matters	3.00	1.365	0.900
11	Personal information of customers is secured with the banks	2.70	1.407	0.902

12	Bank management is easily accessible to customers for help	2.61	1.361	0.860
13	Banks sanction sufficient amount of loan as per requirement	2.80	1.325	0.849
14	Banks provide good counter service in branches	2.48	1.123	0.868
15	Banks staff have empathy towards customers in resolving their issues	2.91	1.278	0.893
16	Bank staff is competent to resolve all queries of customers	2.80	1.396	0.946

Source: Designed by the authors

The critical value of Pearson correlation coefficient for degree of freedom (DF) at the significance level of 0.05 is 0.195 (As mentioned in the table of Critical Values for Pearson's Correlation Coefficient). In our findings the observed values are above 0.8 which are far above the critical value which is 0.195.

The correlations indicated in above table are quite strong, showing that satisfaction with corporate policies and procedures has an impact on overall customers' satisfaction with financial institution.

Conclusion and Suggestions

According to a review of scientific research, satisfaction with commercial banks' policies and procedures for MSMEs is a critical factor in the relationship between a bank and an MSME. There are other researchers who argue that consumers' happiness with commercial banks' policies on MSMEs is an important factor that influences overall customer satisfaction with the financial services provider.

The mean values in the above table show that MSMEs consider banks trustworthy in dealing with important matters. They find online banking services very useful. The borrowers are to a large extent satisfied with the banks' loan sanctioning procedures. However, they are not satisfied with the counter service at branches. The employees are not much willing to help the customers and the bank management is not easily accessible to resolve their issues. The MSMEs seem to be very apprehensive about the security of their information shared by them with the banks. Banks need to take various steps to increase satisfaction level of MSME borrowers. When

banks update and introduce new documents for loan, they don't discard the old and obsolete forms. The loan documentation should be minimum and unnecessary documents and information should not be demanded. The banks should have a check-list for each type of loan proposal and all requirements should be informed to the proponent at the first instance. This will make the loan sanctioning process easy and fast. The banks need to have a system wherein all loan applications are entered in their website and the progress in sanction of loan is visible to the applicant. This will make the loan sanctioning process more transparent. On-line banking services are becoming more and more popular but the borrower customers are getting these services in a restricted way. The banks need to activate their R&D department so as to make this service more useful and customer friendly, particularly for the borrowers. Banks should take borrowers into confidence before sharing their information with chartered accountants, stock auditors, valuers etc., in order to enhance their trustworthiness. Banks need to impart requisite training to their staff to equip them with competence, but it is more important to impart attitudinal and behavioural training to ensure that they have a sympathetic attitude to help and extend willing cooperation to the customers. The bank management should not only be easily accessible but should proactively intervene in case of any hassles faced by the customers.

The above steps can go a long way in increasing satisfaction level of MSME borrowers which in turn will help in extension of higher levels of financial facilities to MSME

sector and their desired growth in the economy.

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